

NATIONAL EVOLUTIONARY SYNTHESIS CENTER

YEAR 4 ANNUAL REPORT

OCTOBER, 2008

NESCENT ANNUAL REPORT YEAR 4

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I YEAR 4 ANNUAL REPORT SUMMARY

During year 4 NESCent continued its maturation as a Center for the promotion of activities leading to a “grand synthesis” in evolutionary biology. The achievements of the Center are detailed in the subsequent sections of this report. Briefly, they include:

- In year 4 the Center functioned with a full complement of postdoctoral fellows. As members of our first cohort reached the end of their terms, they were all successful in finding tenure track faculty positions or high quality postdoctoral positions. We had fewer sabbatical scholars than in the past, but initiated a successful short term visiting scholar program. Our group of in house scientists has continued to be highly interactive, with a large number of activities. One of the most notable was the “synthaton” in which a group of postdocs, and EOG and informatics staff collaborated to produce a review on “what is synthetic evolutionary biology”?
- We have hosted a variety of meetings over the past 10 months (as year 4 is not yet complete) including over 30 meetings of NESCent funded working, catalysis, informatics and education groups. We have also hosted several additional groups, bringing a total of over 650 scientists to the Center over the past 10 months. NESCent sponsored activities have already contributed to significant advances in evolutionary biology.
- We have an outstanding Informatics program, with excellent staff and the full range of infrastructural services to support our scientific programs.
- The Informatics staff has supported in-house and visiting scientists in a variety of ways, and has partnered with external groups to obtain two external awards (NSF INTEROP and DRYAD proposals), with an additional proposal still in review (DataNetOne).
- The Center, in partnership with the Metadata Research Center at UNC Chapel Hill, has completed phase I of the development of DRYAD so that a data repository is now functional. We have worked with societies to come closer to our aim of Society/Journal management of the program.
- Our Education and Outreach group has continued activities in its major areas of focus. An NSF grant to develop innovative curricular materials for evolutionary biology has been awarded (CCLI phase 1 – “Show me the Evolution!”). Our EOG group has partnered with some of the most important individuals in evolutionary education to further the development of teaching material and pedagogical advances.
- The EOG group has completed a number of highly successful outreach activities, including co-sponsoring a symposium on modern evolutionary biology at the National Association of Biology Teachers annual conference and a program at the Society for the Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans in Science meeting,
- We have offered a variety of training opportunities and courses, ranging from advanced computational techniques, to a postdoctoral fellow professional development series to a workshop in teaching evolutionary biology to elementary school students.
- We have a broad range of activities directed towards the recruitment of underrepresented groups into evolutionary biology. These activities span all branches of the Center.
- The administrative infrastructure of the Center has continued to develop to efficiently and effectively support NESCent sponsored science. Substantial effort has been devoted to review and renewal activities.

II YEAR 4 IN NESCENT'S DEVELOPMENT AS A NATIONAL CENTER

Year 4 has been an important year for the Center. It is a year in which we reached an equilibrium, with sufficient staff, infrastructure and a critical mass of supported activities to begin to meet our major aims:

- Support and enable synthetic research in evolutionary biology
- Develop & disseminate new tools for evolutionary informatics
- Take the lead in promoting a culture of data sharing
- Increase the public understanding of science
- Broaden the demographics of evolutionary biology

We believe we have reached the state where we are now functioning fully towards their continuing achievement of these goals.

In year 4 we spent considerable time in self-reflection in preparation for and in response to the site visit. During this process we have identified a number of important issues for further development and consideration – some of which are in progress, and some of which may have to wait for the renewal. The process of planning for the renewal has caused us to critically examine what we do well, and what we might do better and differently.

In year 4 we held our second “community summit” (the first being the “Wilmington meeting”). This summit, held August 11-13, included our Senior Advisory Board and a wide variety of representatives from the evolutionary biology community. The discussions revealed areas of misunderstanding about NESCent, identified areas of great importance to the community, and provided many specific and broad suggestions about further development. These considerations will play a major role in our planning for NESCent's future.

In year 4 we began to focus on developing means for both formative and summative assessment. Some of the increased focus arises from the fact that we have been in operation long enough, with enough data, to make certain types of assessment worthwhile. Some of our new attention is a result of productive comments arising from the site visit. In addition we are reaching the deployment of our administrative database, which should provide complete data on basic demographics and research areas for applicants, funded scientists and visitors. Our projects module should allow increased analysis of the results of NESCent science (see the very interesting results of a preliminary study in section III below). We have established a collaboration with Professor Jonathon Cummings from Duke's Business school, and with Professor Cummings are in the process of developing a “formative” evaluation of NESCent activities, which should provide us with a way to assess collaboration and cultural change. We expect to present a well developed assessment plan as part of our renewal.

III SCIENCE AND SYNTHESIS: ACTIVITIES, FINDINGS AND ACCOMPLISHMENTS

Synthetic research in evolutionary biology occurs along a continuum in terms of the scope of the scientific questions, tools and disciplines that may be involved. At one end of the continuum, synthesis involves integrating available data and models to address important problems within a discipline. Such research is essential for quantitatively evaluating the current state of a field, revealing important general patterns and results, and identifying critical gaps and promising directions for future research. At the other end, methods and perspectives from multiple disciplines are combined to develop new tools for answering – and creating new – fundamental scientific questions. NESCent's strategy for Science and Synthesis is to development and support a portfolio of scientific activities that spans this spectrum of synthetic research in evolutionary biology and related fields.

Towards achieving this scientific portfolio, Science and Synthesis at NESCent has focused on five major goals during the past year: a) to maintain effective and open application and review processes; b) to attract and support a diverse and high-quality portfolio of research projects; c) to establish a vibrant and collegial in-house research community; d) to develop new scientific initiatives that broaden NESCent's reach and scope; e) to assess and ensure the productivity and impact of NESCent scientific activities. As summarized below, we have achieved or made significant progress on each of these goals during the past year.

A. Application and review processes

1. Our on-line application, review and Board evaluation systems have been updated and these systems are now fully integrated with NESCent's more comprehensive administrative database. We have established a regular schedule for applications, with deadlines of 15 June and 1 December each year for working groups, catalysis meetings, and sabbatical scholars, 1 Dec for postdoc applications, and 1 July, April, July and September for short term visitors. The guidelines for proposals, criteria for evaluation, and conflict of interest policies, are all available on our web site.
2. The Science Review Board is now 18 members, and maintaining the excellence and diversity of the Board in terms of field, rank, gender and background is a high priority (see current membership at http://www.nescent.org/dir/science_board.php). We will add several new board members this fall as founding board members continue to rotate off at the end of their 3-year terms.
3. Our new Short-term Visitors program supports short visits to NESCent by faculty and other scientists for 2 weeks to 3 months. We have had 8 Short-term Visitors this past year.

B. Scientific Activities and New Initiatives

1. Application deadlines in year 3 (Dec 07 and June 08) attracted 48 proposals, and resulted in 19 awards (see Table 1 for summary). (Each proposal is ranked as Hi Priority, Fund if Funds Available, or Do Not Fund.)

Table 1. Science applications, year 4

Type	Proposals	Hi Priority	FIFA	Do Not Fund	Offer	Accept
Postdoc	25	6	13	6	10	5
Sabbatical	5	3	2	0	4	4
Working Group	11	3	5	3	4	4
Catalysis Meeting	7	3	3	1	4	4
Total	48	15	23	10	19	17

2. The complete listing of NESCent scientific projects funded in year 3 is given in appendix 1. Collectively, they address a diversity of fundamental evolutionary questions in evolution, systematics and comparative biology. Table 2 summarizes the NESCent awards in year 4 in terms of subject areas (each proposal is classified in terms of two major research areas). We are particularly encouraged by the increased representation in development and in physiology in this year's awards. Table 3 summarizes the cumulative NESCent awards in years 1-4 in terms of subject areas. This summary demonstrates that our scientific research portfolio includes a wide range of approaches and biological levels of organization within evolutionary biology and associated fields.

Table 2. Science awards, Subject areas: year 4 only

<u>Subject area:</u>	<u>Area 1</u>	<u>Area 2</u>
Genomics/Proteomics	1	2
Molecular evolution	1	1
Development	3	1
Physiology/Functional Morphology	3	1
Behavior/Neurobiology	1	1
Evolutionary Ecology/Population Biology	2	4
Evolutionary Genetics	3	1
Phylogeography/Speciation	2	1
Comparative Biology	1	5
Systematics/Phylogenetics	0	2
Paleontology	1	0
Education	1	0

Table 3. Science awards, Subject areas: years 1-4

<u>Subject area:</u>	<u>Area 1</u>	<u>Area 2</u>
Genomics/Proteomics	8	8
Molecular evolution	3	9
Development	3	3
Physiology/Functional Morphology	7	5
Behavior/Neurobiology	4	3
Evolutionary Ecology/Population Biology	10	11
Applied Evolution	2	2
Evolutionary Genetics	10	7
Phylogeography/Speciation	5	5
Comparative Biology	8	11
Systematics/Phylogenetics	9	9
Paleontology	7	2
Education	4	3

3. We have established an optional third year of funding for postdoctoral fellows. Fellows may apply for a third year funding; these proposals are evaluated by the Science Review Board and the Operations Committee. Proposals are evaluated based on the accomplishments of the applicants during their first two years, and the potential that additional funding will enable fellows to expand their projects in exciting new directions. Three postdoctoral fellows were awarded a 3rd-year funding in year 3, and three were awarded in year 4. Our postdoctoral scholars have continued to be successful in finding positions, with scholars accepting tenure track positions at University of Florida, California State University, Los Angeles, University of Oregon, Oregon State University, and postdoctoral positions at University College London, and University of California, Davis during the past year (see appendix 4 for full list of current positions of former NESCent postdoctoral fellows).

4. We have established a vibrant and collegial community of in-house scientists. During year 4 this has included 15 postdoctoral fellows, 6 sabbatical scholars, 3 Triangle Sabbatical Scholars, and several visiting and resident scientists (See appendix 2 for a full list of scientists at the Center in year 4). This community has a regular seminar series (appendix 3), a professional development series for postdocs, a journal club and several reading groups, active intranet communications, a Darwin Day scientific symposium, and a variety of social traditions.

5. Based on input from the site visit and advisory board, we have developed and implemented a revised mentoring system for postdocs. This system includes an initial meeting for each entering postdoc with a mentoring committee to discuss the postdoc's research plans, NESCent expectations, and local and other resources; and the development of a mentoring and collaboration plan for each postdoc.

5. We have supported and hosted 23 meetings by catalysis and working groups during the past year, including meetings by all of the groups funded in the first round of year 4 award. In

addition we have hosted a variety of meetings of groups involved in evolutionary synthesis not supported by NESCent funds (appendix 5). Participant lists may be found in appendices 6-8 and the demographics of funded scientists in appendices 9a-f.

Table 4. meetings and visitors in various activities years 1-4

Year	Science	Education	Informatics	Advisory	Hosted	Total	Total w/o Hosted
Yr 1 Visitors	85	15	0	28	138	266	128
Yr 1 Meetings	4	2	0	3	4	13	9
Yr 2 Visitors	288	13	16	37	174	528	354
Yr 2 Meetings	14	1	1	3	5	24	19
Yr 3 Visitors	452	98	62	23	218	853	635
Yr 3 Meetings	29	5	2	2	10	48	38
Yr 4 Visitors	384	107	29	63	80	663	583
Yr 4 Meetings	23	4	1	3	6	37	31
Yrs 1-4 Visitors	1209	233	107	151	610	2310	1700
Yrs 1-4 Meetings	70	12	4	11	25	122	97

Note: year 4 only includes information as of mid-September, and therefore does not reflect total year 4 activities. Science activities represent activities funded through our sponsored science. Scheduled meetings for the rest of year 4 and early year 5 are in appendix 10.

C. Products

We continue to collect information on the productivity of NESCent research and Table 5 summarizes the number of publications, grants, software and other products, as reported by participants in NESCent projects via our web reporting system, through February 2008. A list of the products reported as of February 2008 may be found at <http://www.nescent.org/science/results.php>. (We are currently collecting updated information on products for year 4.)

Table 5. Products from NESCent science projects, cumulative through February 2008
Numbers of parentheses indicate submitted papers or proposals.

Products:	Postdoc	Sabbatical	Work Group	Catalysis Meetings	Other	Totals
Publications	11(6)	33(4)	18(11)	2(2)	6(4)	70(28)
Grants	3(2)	3	3(1)	2(7)	2(4)	13(14)
Software	8	1	3(1)	0	9	21(1)
Collaborations	14	5	4	6	10	39

Sarah Carrier, a graduate student in Library Sciences (UNC), has recently completed a survey of NESCent publications from years 1-3 that compares attributes of each NESCent publication with those of three non-NESCent publications randomly chosen from the same issue of the same journal. Each NESCent and non-NESCent paper was compared in terms of citation impact factor, number of authors, number of disciplines (assayed by departments: e.g. Biology vs Chemistry), and number of institutions (e.g. Duke vs. UNC-CH). A preliminary analysis suggests that there are consistent mean differences between NESCent and non-NESCent publications in terms of collaboration and impact (Table 6). Small sample size and heterogeneity of the data preclude formal statistical analyses at this stage, but this initial survey suggests that, on average, NESCent publications have higher citation impact and involve greater collaboration among authors, disciplines and institutions than comparable, non-NESCent publications.

Table 6. Citations and collaboration for NESCent and non-NESCent publications, through February 2008.

Metric:	NESCent publication	non-NESCent publication
Citation impact factor	5.44	3.83
# of authors	4.99	4.15
# of disciplines	3.19	2.46
# of institutions	3.34	2.34

Carrier's survey also revealed that publications involving NESCent research were underreported to NESCent by more than 25%. Underreporting of collaborations resulting from NESCent activities is probably even greater. We will be working in year 5 to improve reporting and to assess collaborations more systematically (see below).

D. Demographics of NESCent sponsored science

In appendices 9a-f demographic, geographic and institutional information on participants in of NESCent supported activities are presented. Our database/proposal system is still not efficiently collecting demographic data on applicants, but we have more detail on the participants of our sponsored meetings. Some brief conclusions (complete data may be found in appendices 9a-f).

Postdoctoral fellows: In year 4 our applicants were 44% female. 40% of our offers went to female applicants, and 20% of the postdoc acceptances were to females (3 females and 2 males declined). The declinations were for a variety of reasons including personal reasons and alternate offers. In year 4, just over 1/3 of the postdocs at the Center were female. Ethnicity data of applicants was entered at a very low rate. Postdoc awards were made to 4 white, non-Hispanic candidates, and one Hispanic candidate.

Sabbatical Scholars and Short term visitors: In year 4 25% of the awards were to females, which was approximately the same percentage as the applicant pool. Of the 20 sabbatical and short term visitor positions awarded, the majority went to white, non-Hispanic scientists, although Asian, Hispanic and African American scientist were also funded.

Participants in NESCent activities: Appendix 9c includes information on the demographics of participants in NESCent sponsored activities. In both the sponsored science meetings (working groups and catalysis meetings), as well as total participants, we had about 30% female participation. Our informatics activities had a higher percentage of males, and the education oriented activities were slightly higher female. The ethnic and racial characteristics of participants in NESCent meetings are shown in figure 1.

Figure 1 shows the ethnic and racial characteristics of all participants at NESCent meetings

As before, we had broad geographical participation in NESCent activities, with participants from most states. In years 1-4 we have had visitors from every state except 4. Our international participation (based on home institution) is approximately 17% in years 1-4. The majority of visitors are from doctorate granting universities (appendix 9e)

E. Priorities for year 5

The goals for science and synthesis for the coming year are to maintain and extend the strength and diversity of our portfolio of scientific activities at NESCent, to ensure their productivity and impact. If our funding is extended we plan to award 5 postdocs, 4 sabbatical scholars and 8 working groups and/or catalysis meetings in year 5. We will also continue to award Short-term visitors as appropriate. We will continue to try to broaden the diversity of scientists funded by NESCent and participants in our activities.

One priority for year 5 is to begin to explore more systematically how NESCent activities promote new collaborations, research and scientific collaborations impact productive and innovative synthetic research in evolution. We have initiated a collaboration with Dr. Jonathan Cummings, a social scientist in the Business School at Duke, to apply social network analysis and related approaches to explore “formative” approaches to the development of scientific collaborations, and we will continue to apply analyses of data available in our administrative database. A Ph.D. student under Dr. Cummings direction will begin working with the Center in January 2009.

Additionally, we will continue our efforts in outreach (appendices 11 & 12) so that all appropriate groups are aware of NESCent funding opportunities.

IV INFORMATICS: INITIATIVES, ACTIVITIES AND ACCOMPLISHMENTS

Our informatics program continues to support sponsored science, pursue significant new initiatives and participate in a large number of national activities. As we receive additional funding from external grants, our staff has grown so that there are now 10 full time informatics staff members.

A. Open software development

A “comparative Phylogenetic Methods in R” hackathon was held Dec 10-14, 2007 at NESCent (<http://precedings.nature.com/documents/2126/version/1>). The event led to better integration and support for R packages used for analysis of ancestral states, diversification, divergence times, tree simulation, trait mapping, and visualization. A common phylogenetic data model was developed and implemented in the new Phylobase data package, which was publicly released in February. Additional outcomes include an active new mailing list for R users interested in phylogenetics, a community wiki with documentation for new users (<http://r-phylo.org>), and prototype integration between R and Mesquite.

Plans for a hackathon in December 2008 are underway, with a focus on database interoperability. This event is being co-organized with, and arises out of the activities of, the Evolutionary Informatics Working Group, which has been promoting new standards for description and exchange of evolutionary data (<http://evoinfo.nescent.org>)

In February, Assistant Director of Informatics Hilmar Lapp participated in BioHackathon 2008 Feb 12-15 in Tokyo. This led to a first draft of specifications for a common Phyloinformatics Web-Services protocol (<http://evoinfo.nescent.org/PhyloWS>) and to the 1.0 release of BioSQL (<http://biosql.org>).

B. Informatics training

The Phyloinformatics Summer Course was held from July 24-Aug 4 (<http://www.nescent.org/courses/2008/comphy/>). Fourteen instructors offered hands-on lessons in how to use and contribute to Java, Perl and R libraries for phylogenetics, as well as advanced tracks in the use of HyPhy, Mesquite, and databases. Thirty-six students were enrolled with a nearly 1:1 ratio of males to females (see participant list in Appendix 7).

NESCent participated for the second year as a mentor organization in the Google Summer of Code (<http://code.google.com/soc/2008>). Six students (one supported by the Phenoscope project) were paired with remote mentors and worked on independent projects in support of open-source software tools in the field. The projects, mentors and students are listed below.

Project: Tree and data plotting in the phylobase project
Student: Peter Cowan, UC Berkeley
Mentor: Ben Bolker, University of Florida

Project: Enhancing the representation of ecophylogenetic tools in R
Student: Matthew Helmus, University of Wisconsin, Madison
Mentor: Steven Kembel, UC Berkeley

Project: Graphviz navigation of databases
Student: Paul McMillan, UC Berkeley
Mentor: Brian O'Meara, NESCent

Project: An Extension of Mesquite based on PDSIMUL
Student: Matt Ackerman, Missouri State University
Mentor: Peter Midford, University of Kansas

Project: SAX based phyloXML support in BioPerl
Student: Mira Han, University of Indiana
Mentor: Chris Fields, University of Illinois, Chicago

Project: Matrix display of phenotype annotations using ontologies in Phenote
Student: Michael Wallinga, University of South Dakota
Mentor: James Balhoff, NESCent
(this last project was funded by the Phenoscape project and not Google)

NESCent also organized and hosted the first GMOD summer school from July 11-13 (http://gmod.org/wiki/GMOD_Summer_School). Participants included 25 students and 4 instructors, from 19 states and 4 countries. The program featured two and half days of hands on training starting with an overview of GMOD and then covering installation and configuration of popular GMOD tools, include Chado, GBrowse, CMap, Apollo, and the Community Annotation System.

C. Data sharing

The Dryad project aims to develop a repository for data underlying publications that interfaces with the journal submission process as well as specialized databases (<http://datadryad.org>). A Phase I system based on DSpace and supported on the core grant was made public in early 2008. A survey of data sharing attitudes and practices among >400 users was conducted in April and the results are being prepared for publication. A special workshop for society and journal representatives was held at the Evolution meetings in Minneapolis in June. Dryad received critical Phase II funding from NSF, starting in September 2008. In addition, funding for additional metadata work to support data indexing and retrieval was awarded from the Institute for Museum and Library Services (PI: Jane Greenberg, UNC). Upcoming major milestones include test integration with the submission process for the first journal (American Naturalist) and the first meeting of the Management Board in early 2008. The consortium of societies and journals continues to grow; the most recent discussions have involved the Society for Paleontology.

D. Model organism database support

NESCent has partnered with the GMOD project to promote, support and develop shared open-source tools for the management of model organism data, particularly to the evolutionary community (<http://gmod.org>). The extensive and decentralized documentation for the project was consolidated, reorganized and moved to a wiki with active newsfeeds in December 2007. Workshops and presentations have been made at a variety of meetings (“Arthropod Genomics” April 10-13 in Kansas City, “IGERT Symposium on Evolution, Development, and Genomics” Apr 4-6 in Eugene, and the American Genetics Association annual meeting June 4-7 in Raleigh). The GMOD summer school is described above. NESCent also helped organize the annual GMOD developers meetings in Toronto prior to ISMB. The NESCent-funded help desk has integrated several new components into GMOD, including Galaxy and Phenote. A user survey is being prepared for Fall 2008.

E. Evolutionary phenotypes

The Phenoscape project is developing computational tools, including ontologies, annotation software, and database standards, that allow researchers to integrate developmental genetic and comparative morphological/anatomical data (<https://www.phenoscape.org/>). Two new ontologies (Teleost Taxonomy Ontology (TTO) and the Teleost Anatomy Ontology (TAO)) were released and are available through the National Center for Biomedical Ontologies BioPortal (<http://bioontology.org/tools/portal/bioportal.html>). An obo-taxonomy mailing list was initiated to discuss the representation of taxonomic names and ranks within ontologies. Multiple releases of the annotation software (Phenote/Phenex) have been made through Sourceforge. A collaboration with the Berkeley Bioinformatics and Ontology Project (PI: Suzi Lewis) has resulted in the rapid prototyping of a central database and query application for the curated phenotype data. Data annotation is underway for 75 papers containing explicit or implicit character matrices for the Ostariophysa. Two data annotation jamborees have been held in 2008 to train new users and fine-tune the curation software and workflow. A one-day “Ontologies and Evolution” workshop was held in conjunction with the Evolution meetings in Minneapolis on June 20th, co-organized with NCBO. The next such workshop is being planned for SICB 2009. Regular progress reports are posted to the project blog at <http://blog.phenoscape.org>.

F. Support of sponsored science and administration

A high priority for this past year was completing development of a new, and more comprehensive, administrative database for the center (covering People, Proposals, Projects, Activities and Products). Major efforts in support of sponsored science included databases in support of the Primate Life History working group (<http://plhdb.nescent.org/plhdb/>), the Plant Mixed Mating System working group (ongoing), and Phanerozoic Body Size Evolution working group (new project). The informatics staff has also worked closely with the Evolutionary Informatics Working Group, particularly in efforts to develop and promote two standards: a Comparative Data and Analysis Ontology (<http://evolutionaryontology.org>) and the NeXML phylogenetic data exchange language (<http://nexml.org>). Postdoctoral scholar Brian O’Meara released the TreeTapper database, a resource cataloging the universe of methods and software in comparative phylogenetics (<http://www.treetrapper.org>); this project was developed in consultation with NESCent informatics and was the recipient of one of the 2008 Google Summer of Code projects. In the area of training, an in-house R short course was organized by and for postdocs, taught by Todd Jobe of UNC.

Notable improvements to NESCent’s services and capabilities include:

- Improved hardware and configuration for in-house filesharing and backups
- Additional cluster-computing capacity (8 new dual quad-core CPUs)
- Now providing OpenID login to online resources for visiting scientists.
- We are now beginning to aggregate NESCent-related blogs and other feeds at <http://planet.nescent.org/>.

G. Additional partnerships and community engagement activities

- NESCent co-sponsored and had multiple presentations at the 2008 ISMB conference (the major annual, international bioinformatics conference) and the satellite Bioinformatics Open Source Conference (BOSC).
- NESCent is partnering with on an INTEROP project “Creation of a Virtual Data Center for the Biodiversity, Ecological and Environmental Sciences” with PI Bill Michener or LTER and co-PI Matt Jones of NCEAS.
- NESCent is partnering with a pending DataNet proposal DataNetOne: Observation Network for Earth” with Michener and many others.
- Lapp and Vision are coorganizing (with Stan Blum) an Ontologies session at the annual meeting of the Biodiversity Information Standards Group (TDWG) in Australia in October. Lapp is also serving as the first lead of a new TDWG Phyloinformatics working group, cosponsored by BioSynC (Biosynthesis Center, EOL project http://www.fieldmuseum.org/research_collections/biosync/scientificmission.asp).
- NESCent was represented at the TraitNet RCN meeting in Dec 2007.
- Vision and Wiegmann co-organized a special session on AToL-EoL coordination at the AToL meeting in March 2008 in New Orleans.
- NESCent co-sponsored and hosted a planning meeting for VertNet, organized by J. Hanken, C. Moritz and D Wake, May 13-14.
- NESCent was represented at the Morphbank Ontology Workshop at Florida State University, May 3-4.
- Vision attended iPlant kickoff meeting at Cold Spring Harbor in April and serves on the steering committee of an iPlant Grand Challenge workshop for plant tree of life planned for November (PI: Donoghue).
- NESCent sponsored Brian O’Meara to serve as an instructor for the Workshop in applied Phylogenetics (March in Bodega Bay).
- NESCent provided financial support for the month-long Analytical Paleontology Summer Course at NCEAS (organized by John Alroy) from June 23rd-July 28th.

H. Notable publications arising from NESCent Informatics activities in 2008

- Barquist L, Holmes I (2008) xREI: a phylo-grammar visualization webserver. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 36:W65-9. (GSoC 2007)
- Holland RC, Down TA, Pocock M, Prlić A, Huen D, James K, Foisy S, Dräger A, Yates A, Heuer M, Schreiber MJ. 2008. BioJava: an open-source framework for bioinformatics. *Bioinformatics* 24:2096-7 (contributions from 2006 hackathon and GSoC 2007)
- Jordan GE, Piel WH (2008) PhyloWidget: web-based visualizations for the tree of life. *Bioinformatics* 24:1641-2. (GSoC 2007)

I. Software products released

For a list of current software products see: <http://www.nescent.org/informatics/software.php>

J. Informatics priorities for year 5

Over the next year, we aim to successfully complete a number of informatics projects in support of our sponsored science projects. The largest of these efforts are databases for the plant mixed mating system working group, the Phanerozoic body size working group, and the primate life history working group. In addition we are supporting the development of trait-based databases for two of the postdocs.

Another priority is to continue the collaborative open-source software community development activities. This will be achieved by planning two more hackathons, the first to be focused on phylogenetic database interoperability and held in December 2008. We also aim to offer at least three summer courses, one in phyloinformatics, one in using GMOD, and a third that is being planned in the area of meta-analysis.

The third area of priority is in the continued development of cyberinfrastructure. We aim to have integration of the Dryad data deposition workflow with test journals and to begin cycles of usability testing and refinement. The Dryad Management Board will also convene to decide upon initial data policies, development priorities, and begin reviewing plans for self-sustainability.

The web database for Phenoscope will be launched and will begin to undergo usability testing and refinement, and a workshop will be held at SICB for community engagement. Additional workshops in the area of technical standards development and community engagement will be held in conjunction with these cyberinfrastructure initiatives, with the INTEROP collaboration and, if funded, with the DataNetONE project.

Finally we hope to complete the initial rollout of the comprehensive administrative database and enter into a phase of maintenance and feature refinement.

V EDUCATION AND OUTREACH: INITIATIVES, ACTIVITIES AND ACCOMPLISHMENTS

The Education and Outreach Group (EOG) at NESCent has continued to focus on key areas of our mission: outreach to the education and science communities, providing resources for educators, and outreach to underrepresented groups. We have worked to develop effective programs, to build collaborations, to expand on established resources, and to take advantage of NESCent's scientific expertise. We also provide a variety of services within NESCent, such as public affairs, web site maintenance, and a regular newsletter (www.nescent.org/news/). We continue to expand our media production, including video capture of presentations, and a podcast program based on the *Evolution in the News* series. EOG is also represented on the editorial board of the Springer journal *Evolution: Education and Outreach* and on the advisory board for the NSF funded expansion of the EvoS program. We have been working with the journal to publicize NESCent's resources for educators, as well as providing articles for the journal based on activities at NESCent. EOG is also on the Education Committee for the Society for the Study of Evolution.

Two new education working groups were initiated this year: Evolution Across the Curriculum (EVAC) and Tree Reasoning in Evolution Education (TREE). Sabbatical scholar Joe Fail repeated his popular summer workshop for teachers. EOG continues to sit in on working groups and catalysis meetings at NESCent, which has resulted in a publication on evolutionary medicine and a symposium on biogeography at NABT. The EOG worked extensively with NESCent's Informatics group this summer on the planning and facilitation of the Computational Phyloinformatics summer course, further strengthening the collaboration and cooperation between these two groups.

A. EOG sponsored and facilitated working groups

The Education and Outreach Group has continued its involvement in several evolution education-related working groups at NESCent. Some of these are sponsored and supported by NESCent's Science and Synthesis branch, but others are actually supported directly through EOG funds. In all cases, every member of the EOG staff is an active participant and plays an important leadership and planning role in the working group's activities.

SELECTION (December 2006, June 2007, May 2008)

This working group was proposed by BioQUEST, a curriculum development consortium, to develop educational resources in evolution using NESCent's scientific resources and connections. EOG personnel Kristin Jenkins and Jory Weintraub, as well as NESCent post-docs Kirsten Fisher, Samantha Price and David Kidd, were active participants. The "Phanerozoic Body Size" working group at NESCent was very interested in developing an educational piece, and EOG arranged for a representative of this working group, Jennifer Stempien, to join the SELECTION group. The third and final meeting of this working group was held at NESCent in May of 2008. As a culmination of this working group's curriculum development activities, a one-day evolution education workshop was held within the three-day meeting. Participants in this workshop were primarily biology instructors from local and regional community colleges, four year colleges and universities and some high schools. During the workshop, participants were introduced to curricular materials developed by the SELECTION working group and strategies for implementation and assessment were shared. Materials from this workshop were also presented at the BioQUEST summer workshop. Products from the SELECTION group

continue to be shared and discussed by both EOG and BioQUEST staff at various teaching and education conferences attended by these individuals.

Evolution Across the Curriculum (EvAC)

This group is addressing the problem of presentation of evolution as a separate and isolated concept in undergraduate science curricula by attempting to develop models which integrate evolution throughout these curricula. In May of 2008 the EvAC group held its second meeting, during which a one-day workshop was held at NESCent. In addition to the EvAC group members (which includes the EOG staff), several invited participants (biology faculty and instructors from local and regional high schools, colleges and universities, as well as science writers) spent the day discussing and developing “EvAC exemplars”. These are short, concise, focused modules which address basic biological concepts (glycolysis, photosynthesis, the immune response, reproduction, conservation biology) from an evolutionary perspective, to demonstrate how all biological events and processes are shaped by evolutionary concepts. At least eight distinct exemplars were developed during this workshop and EOG staff are taking the lead on refining these for piloting and implementation. This working group has also resulted in the preparation of an NSF RCN grant proposal (in review currently), as well as an NSF CCLI Phase II grant (in preparation), both of which will, in part, continue to address and further the work of the EvAC working group. EvAC will hold its third and final NESCent meeting in the Spring of 2009, during which strategies for implementation of exemplars will be discussed, broader problems of curriculum policy reform will be addressed and ideas for future directions will be covered.

Tree Reasoning in Evolution Education (TREE)

This group focuses on identifying and addressing the misconceptions surrounding the use and interpretation of phylogenetic trees. The group involves EOG and NESCent researchers and held their second meeting in May of 2008. The foci of this meeting were to meet with NESCent Informatics staff to discuss TREE resource databases and prototyping, and to continue to define key challenges in addressing student understanding and interpretation of trees. This group will hold its third and final meeting at NESCent in Spring, 2009.

B. EOG partnerships with NESCent Science Working Groups

EOG staff members participate in each NESCent sponsored working group or catalysis meeting. This assists us in disseminating the results of these groups, and also leads to potential collaborations. Several such collaborations have been initiated.

The EOG staff has been working with members of the “Phanerozoic Body Size Trends in Time and Space” working group and NESCent Informatics staff to develop an educational component of the databases the working group is generating. Jennifer Stempien, a member of the working group who is doing a postdoc in science education, is coordinating this effort with EOG.

The EOG staff has worked with Joel Cracraft, an organizer of the working group “Developing an Integrative Algorithmic Method for Historical Biogeography,” to develop and schedule a workshop in biogeography at the 2008 NABT conference, which will be held in Memphis, TN in October of 2009. EOG handled proposal submission, all of the logistics of setting up the half-day workshop, and participated in discussion and planning for the content of the workshop.

Several members of the Plant EvoGenetics working group expressed interest in educational activities ranging from bioinformatics to outreach to underrepresented minorities. EOG has

introduced participants of this meeting to others for potential collaborations and will continue to look for opportunities to take advantage of this group's interest.

C. EOG Programs

NESCent Minority Outreach

The EOG has continued its strong focus on diversifying evolution by initiating or participating in a wide variety of activities and programs targeting underrepresented students. These activities include:

- Organization and administration of a suite of activities focusing on evolution and ecology at the annual meeting of SACNAS (the Society for the Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans in Science). At the Oct. 2008 conference, these activities will include organization of a scientific symposium (featuring scientific presentations by NESCent and NCEAS postdocs), a career and professional mentoring session entitled “Conversations with Scientists” which will feature discussions with a large number of evolutionary biologists and ecologists, and a screening and discussion of the global warming/climate change documentary “The 11th Hour”. These activities are a collaboration of NESCent EOG, NCEAS, AIBS and the Society for the Study of Evolution, and once again EOG staff have been successful in obtaining additional funding and outside support from the academic publisher Springer.
- In 2008 a collaboration with Drs. Scott Edwards and Rich Kliman on an NSF funded program known as “Undergraduate Diversity at Evolution” was initiated. This program identifies talented undergraduate students (with a focus on underrepresented students) and provides travel awards so that they can attend the annual meeting of SSE/SSB/ASN. At the May, 2008 meeting in Minneapolis, MN twenty one students attended the meeting, participated in a special poster session at which they presented their own research, and received mentoring from evolutionary biologists. NESCent provided financial, organizational and logistical support, as well as several mentors for the undergraduate students. As per discussions with Dr. Edwards, EOG will take an increasingly prominent role in organization and administration of this program in coming years.
- Ongoing collaboration with NESCent’s “targeted sabbatical scholars”. NESCent has continued to offer a targeted sabbatical fellowship for faculty from minority serving institutions and 2008 saw the arrival of the third such sabbatical scholarship – Dr. Christian D’Orgeix of Virginia State University. Dr. D’Orgeix was originally invited to participate in NESCent activities as a member of the EOG’s *EEHMU* (Evolution Education at Historically Minority Universities) working group. As a result of this participation, Dr. D’Orgeix was encouraged to apply for the sabbatical fellowship which began in Sept. 2008. During his year long sabbatical, he will be working with EOG staff on development of several education related initiatives, including development of a new Evolution course for students at his home institution.
- EOG staff members have been acting as mentors to Bruce Boller, who is a high school biology teacher at Bertie High School in rural Windsor, NC. Mr. Boller is a recipient of a prestigious Kenan Fellowship and, with assistance and mentorship from EOG staff, is developing and implementing new evolution curriculum in his school, which has a large majority of African American and Hispanic students. Discussion for continued EOG

outreach to his educational community (beyond his Kenan Fellowship project) are underway.

Evolution in the News

This year EOG formed a collaboration with Understanding Evolution to enhance the Evolution in the News program. The stories are selected from the popular literature on a monthly basis and the key evolutionary concepts of the story are explained in an illustrated text piece. EOG then develops a video or audio podcast interview with a scientist who works on a related subject. Links to primary and popular literature, as well as classroom activities and lessons are provided. In conjunction with Understanding Evolution, EOG has been awarded an NSF CCLI phase 1 grant to evaluate and improve the Evolution in the News program. This podcast-enhanced Evolution in the News program will be a key component in an upcoming CCLI Phase 2 proposal to develop an “Undergraduate Lounge” section of the Understanding Evolution program. This section will cater to undergraduate students and teachers, and will be web 2.0 intensive.

NABT Annual Professional Development Conference

As we have for the last several years, EOG is collaborating with AIBS to organize and deliver a symposium on evolutionary biology at the annual conference of the National Association of Biology Teachers (NABT). At this year’s conference (which is being held in Memphis, TN in October of 2008), in addition to the half-day symposium (entitled “Illuminating Biology: An Evolutionary Perspective”) NESCent and AIBS will, for the first time, be offering a half-day, hands-on workshop for teachers to provide them with tools and resources for teaching the concepts presented in the evolution symposium. This workshop is being developed in collaboration with the BioQUEST Curriculum Consortium and UCMP’s Understanding Evolution website group.

Additionally, EOG staff have worked with Joel Cracraft to organize and develop a half-day workshop on Biogeography, and also with the Society for the Study of Evolution to plan another workshop entitled “Using Free, Intuitive Software to Explore Mysteries of Evolutionary History in the High School Biology Classroom”.

Post-Doctoral Professional Development Program

The post-doctoral professional development program was designed to provide NESCent post-doctoral fellows with career development information and opportunities they might miss in this non-traditional position. EOG organizes this program and identifies appropriate speakers in topics ranging from career advice to use of technology in teaching. These sessions are open to the public and often have postdocs and graduate students from local Universities in attendance. Sabbatical faculty and the Center Directors have provided valuable career advice in special sessions of the NESCent informal seminar series. Media specialists have provided training in communicating with the media and the public. EOG has provided information about resources for post-doctoral fellows, such as the Duke Post-Doctoral Association, as well as training in teaching. EOG also coordinates the visiting lecturers program which provides postdocs with the opportunity to give lectures in person at local institutions, including HMUs; remote lectures are also an option via videoconferencing. EOG staff have also provided individual and group consulting to postdocs on topics such as effective teaching, developing a Teaching Philosophy statement, scientific writing and delivering effective presentations.

Support of Center Activities

EOG also provides a variety of in house services at NESCent that support the aims of outreach and education. These include the organization of the Friday seminar series, providing NESCent website content (appendix 14), including stories and news items, NESCent's quarterly newsletter production, serving as press officers for the Center, production and supply of posters/postcards/ads and booth orders for conferences, videoconferencing, video streaming of seminars and other presentations.

Celebrating Darwin's Bicentennial

EOG has played a large role in organizing the annual Darwin Day Symposium and this year's symposium focuses on applications of evolution for a general public audience. EOG will offer a teacher workshop prior to the symposium based on the same topics to be presented at the symposium. In addition, NESCent is co-sponsoring a speaker series with the local PBS station, WUNC, the North Carolina Museum of Natural History, and the Keck Center at North Carolina State University. EOG is taking the lead in organizing this series which will feature Carl Zimmer on Darwin's birthday, as well as other prominent local scientists throughout the year. NESCent has also collaborated with WUNC and the theatre department at North Carolina State University to produce the play "RE:Darwin" based on the correspondence between Darwin and Asa Gray. The play will be performed in November, 2009 and EOG will identify a panel of scientists for follow-up discussions. EOG is also working with COPUS on the 2009 Year of Science website, specifically providing materials for February – Evolution month.

D. Priorities for year 5

In addition to continuing the very successful programs discussed above, in year 5 the EOG has a number of priorities for new activities.

- With respect to our minority outreach efforts, we plan to bring all of them under the umbrella of a single initiative focusing on *Diversity in Evolution*. We will assemble a group of experts (consisting of members of our EEHMU working group, new NESCent minority outreach collaborators such as Scott Edwards and Rich Kliman, and others) to examine our efforts, identify successes and determine future paths for continuing and expanding our minority outreach and *Diversity in Evolution* efforts. These efforts will also build on and strengthen our existing relationships with the minority outreach efforts of other centers and professional societies, such as NCEAS, AIBS, SSE, and ESA, as additional avenues for collaboration are identified and pursued.
- Based on our previous experiences at the NABT conference, we intend to explore expanding our interactions with additional groups such as the National Science Teachers Association (NSTA) regional meetings and also select state science teacher conferences.
- Building on recent discussions with education/outreach groups from several other large scale biology programs and centers (including NCEAS, EoL and iPlant), we propose to organize and host a catalysis meeting to coordinate education and outreach efforts. This meeting will focus on identifying fertile areas for overlap, common goals and objectives and complementary programs and initiatives.
- Building on the success of past EOG workshops (as well as our successful collaboration this past year on our Informatics group's *Computational Phyloinformatics* summer

course), we plan to organize and deliver a week-long summer course for middle-school/high-school biology teachers focusing on evolution science and pedagogy. This course, which will be offered for continuing education credit, will provide in-service teachers with a review/overview of evolutionary biology (basic concepts and “hot topics”) and will also focus on best practices related to science pedagogy, drawing on the EOG staff’s strengths in the scholarship of science teaching and learning (SSTL).

VI SUMMARY OF YEAR 4 CENTER ACTIVITIES TO INCREASE PARTICIPATION OF MEMBERS OF UNDERREPRESENTED GROUPS

Although many activities to increase the participation of underrepresented groups into science were discussed in the above report from our Education and Outreach group, we here summarize overall center activities. It is important to emphasize that this is a Center-wide commitment that permeates all of the center’s activities. Specific activities in year 4 included:

In year 4 NESCent sponsored the scientific work of several outstanding evolutionary biologists who are also African American or Hispanic, and members from these groups are also on our advisory boards.

Professor Christian D’Orgeix from Virginia State University has been supported as a targeted sabbatical scholar

Professor Joe Fail from Johnson C. Smith University, a former targeted sabbatical scholar was supported by Duke University funds to again provide his summer workshop for local elementary school teachers in evolutionary biology.

Our student research internship (see Appendix 13) has brought 12 undergraduates, including many women and two African American students to the Center; 8 graduate students; and 2 students who recently graduated, for a total of 28 student research internships.

Our Computational Phyloinformatics course offered travel awards to students from under-represented groups in an attempt to attract additional students from these populations. The course had almost 50% women students, who are highly under-represented in computational biology.

We developed an impressive set of programs for the SACNAS (Society for the Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans in Science) meeting as detailed in the EOG report. This program has been highly successful. We also worked with Scott Edwards and Rich Kliman to develop a mentorship program to bring students from under-represented groups to the Evolution meetings.

Our evolution in the news Podcast proposal is in part targeted towards students from under-represented groups.

VII NESCENT ADMINISTRATION

The development of NESCent as a functioning center has continued in year 4. Major administrative activities and accomplishments include the following:

A. Community summit and NESCent Senior Advisory Board meeting

In September of 2008 we held a community summit attended by about 40 evolutionary biologists drawn from around the country. This meeting was coordinated with our Senior Advisory Board meeting. This provided useful feedback on NESCent programs and potential future activities. The Board endorsed the idea of working towards a combined SAB and Science Review Boards, and we will begin to merge these functions at our fall meeting.

B. Administrative Infrastructure

Administrative Database

We have continued to work on the development of our administrative database, and are near full deployment. Currently minor problems are being corrected; legacy data is being entered and curated; and the development of the reports system is being finalized.

New Hires

NESCent has continued to fill needs for staff. We now have an informatics staff of eight individuals (not including Vision), and with commitments on newly funded grants, we will be hiring several more individuals. With the CCLI grant we will be recruiting an additional postdoc to focus on outreach activities. We are recruiting an additional financial manager (part time) to manage increased financial tracking arising from external grants. Finally, we are currently negotiating with an individual for our Assistant Director of Science position. We have hired two excellent new staff members (logistics coordinator and staff assistant) to replace departed staff members. Our current organizational chart may be found in appendix 15.

University support

During the last year we have completed a new Memorandum of Agreement among the Universities; this MOA was submitted as a part of our site visit report. Additionally, we have received increased direct support from the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, in the form of direct financial support for Associate Director Vision, and from North Carolina State University in the form of renegotiated overhead rates, and direct support for Associate Director Wiegmann.

VIII PRODUCTS FROM NESCENT FUNDED ACTIVITIES IN YEAR 4

To our dismay we found that the email to NESCent sponsored scientists requesting an update on products that was to have gone out in August, did not go out. We are currently collecting the data on all products generated in year 4. Products as of February, 2008 may be found on our webpage <http://www.nescent.org/science/results.php> and we will send an updated list when it has been have been compiled.

IX CENTER PARTNERSHIPS AND ASSOCIATIONS

In years 1-3 NESCent developed a rich network of partnerships, reported in previous annual reports. In year 4 we continued many of these activities. Below we summarize only specific activities with these partners and new partnerships in year 4.

We have continued an active collaboration with the Encyclopedia of Life (EoL) Initiative, with collaborations with their informatics, education and outreach groups, and the Biodiversity Synthesis center (BioSYNC). We will be working with the BioSYNC to co-sponsor a hosted event or reception at the SICB 2009 meeting in Boston to share information with conference attendees about funding opportunities within our organizations.

<http://www.eol.org>

Together with the EoL, NESCent organized discussions at the 2008 AToL meeting to address issues of collaboration between AToL projects and EoL.

<http://atol.sdsc.edu>

NESCent has also co-organized (with Nico Cellinese) a phyloinformatics workshop to be held at the 2008 TDWG meeting that is being sponsored by the EoL BioSYNC. In addition, NESCent is organizing and sponsoring an ontologies session at 2008 TDWG meeting (and is an institutional member of that organization).

<http://www.tdwg.org>

Associate Director of Informatics Vision attended the iPlant kickoff meeting in April and is on the steering committee for an iPlant Grand Challenge Workshop on Assembling the Plant Tree of Life. Our EOG group has had initial conversations with this Collaborative about future collaborations, specifically between the education/outreach groups.

<http://iplantcollaborative.org>

NESCent continues to work with NCEAS in a variety of ways, including the co-sponsorship of working groups. The Directors of NCEAS, the iPlant collaborative and NIMBioS met during the NESCent community summit to discuss ways to establish, continue and increase collaborative programs.

<http://nimbios.org>

<http://www.nceas.ucsb.edu>

In May of 2008 NESCent co-sponsored a meeting with the Museum of Comparative Zoology at Harvard University to set forth the planning for a joint VertNet database, including the development of community standards and a long term sustainability plan for the most important museum vertebrate databases (HerpNet, ORNIS, MaNis and BioGeomancer). This meeting resulted in the establishment of a steering committee and the garnering of initial funds to begin the integration of these databases.

<http://www.herpnet.org/>

<http://www.specifysoftware.org/Informatics/informaticsornis/>

<http://manisnet.org/>

<http://www.biogeomancer.org/>

NESCent continued its ongoing partnership with the Generic Model Organism Database (GMOD) through activities such as organization of the annual project meeting in Toronto and organized and hosting of the first-ever GMOD summer school.

<http://www.gmod.org>

Through the Phenoscope project, NESCent co-sponsored a 1-day workshop on Evolution and Ontologies with the National Center for Biomedical Ontologies (NCBO), and continued working in collaboration with the Open Biomedical Ontologies (OBO) consortium and the Zebrafish Information Network (ZFIN). The center also hosted a summer internship in phenotype informatics supported by the DeepFin RCN.

<http://www.bioontology.org>

<http://www.obofoundry.org>

<http://zfin.org>

<http://www.deepfin.org>

NESCent's Dryad data sharing initiative has received an NSF DBI award that is funding a collaboration among the UNC School of Information & Library Sciences Metadata Research Center, the North Carolina State University Digital Libraries Initiative, the LTER Network, and TreeBASE. The initiative is in partnership with major evolutionary biology and ecology societies, including the American Society of Naturalists, the Ecological Society of America, the Society for the Study of Evolution, the Society for Integrative and Comparative Biology, the Society for Molecular Biology and Evolution, the Paleontology Society, the Society of Systematic Biologists, and the European Society for Evolutionary Biology, as well as independent journals such as Molecular Ecology, Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution, and Evolutionary Applications.

<http://ils.unc.edu/mrc>

<http://www.lib.ncsu.edu/dli>

<http://www.lternet.edu>

<http://www.treebase.org>

NESCent is one of the coordinating institutions on a recent NSF INTEROP award that funds an informatics partnership with the LTER network, NCEAS, the Oak Ridge National Laboratory Distributed Active Archive Center, the USGS National Biological Information Infrastructure and the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF). We are also a coordinating institution in a pending DataNet proposal that involves a network of over 20 partner organizations working on shared infrastructure for Earth-based environmental observation data.

<http://www-eosdis.ornl.gov>

<http://www.nbi.gov>

<http://www.gbif.org>

With Google's sponsorship, we hosted five students in the 2008 Google Summer of Code program.

<http://code.google.com/soc/2008/>

NESCent co-sponsored the Paleobiology Database summer course and the Bodega Bay applied phylogenetics workshop.

<http://paleodb.org/cgi-bin/bridge.pl?user=Guest&action=displayHomePage>

http://bodegaphylo.wikispot.org/Front_Page

NESCent's Assistant Director of Informatics participated in a hackathon focused on web services for bioinformatics, sponsored by the Database Center for Life Sciences in Japan.

<http://hackathon.dbcls.jp>

The 2007 Comparative Methods in R Hackathon involved a working partnership with the developers from multiple open-source programming packages, detailed at the R-phylo wiki:

<http://r-phylo.org>

We have worked with the Society for the Study of Evolution (SSE) on several projects, including the development of DRYAD, co-sponsorship of NESCent's SACNAS activities, and cosponsorship of the presentation at the NABT annual meeting. An EOG staff member is a member of the SSE Education Committee. Our collaboration with SSE continues to expand. They have committed to regular support of the SACNAS events and they sponsor a presentation at NABT by SSE members which EOG arranges. In addition to serving on the Education Committee we are involved in the development of the teacher workshop associated with the annual conference, and host the "Evolution, Science and Society" website originally posted on EvoNet. |

<http://www.evolutionsociety.org>

The American Institute of Biological Science (AIBS) has continued to be an active partner with NESCent from the start. Currently they are co-sponsors of both the NABT Evolution Symposium and NESCent's SACNAS activities.

<http://www.aibs.org/core/index.html>

We worked with the Biotechnology Center Institute (BTCI) on their Bioethics Forum "Evolution in the 21st Century" and they have expressed interest in a 2009 summer teacher's workshop on evolution.

<http://www.btc.org/bioethics/default.html>

We are participating with the North Carolina Museum of Natural History in their Science Café series. We have expanded our collaborations with NCMNH to include a year-long speaker series and a co-sponsorship of a Darwin-themed stage production (entitled "Re: Design") as part of the 2009 "Year of Darwin" activities. WUNC-TV (local PBS affiliate) and NC State University's Theater Department are also collaborating on these "Year of Darwin" projects.

<http://www.naturalsciences.org>

<http://www.unctv.org>

<http://www.ncsu.edu/theatre>

We are participating with the Coalition for the Public Understanding of Science (COPUS) in public education initiatives. We are working with COPUS to populate the 2009 Year of Science site, specifically February – Evolution month.

<http://www.copusproject.org>

We have collaborated with BioQUEST to develop problem sets and present material at teacher workshops.

<http://www.bioquest.org/index.php>

We have collaborated with Understanding Evolution to write a successful CCLI Phase 1 proposal to assess and improve the Evolution in the News program. We are also collaborating on a CCLI Phase 2 proposal to develop a web 2.0 rich "Undergraduate Lounge."

<http://evolution.berkeley.edu/>

We are serving on the advisory board for the NSF funded EvoS program expansion.

<http://evolution.binghamton.edu/evos/>

We are collaborating with Scott Edwards (Harvard) and Rich Kliman (Cedar Crest College) to sponsor, organize and facilitate an NSF-funded program which awards undergraduates (primarily from underrepresented groups) travel awards to attend the annual Evolution (SSE/SSB/ASN) conference. While at the conference the students receive mentoring and professional development and present their research at an undergraduate poster session.

<http://www.oeb.harvard.edu/faculty/edwards/community>
<http://www2.cedarcrest.edu/academic/bio/rkliman>

We are collaborating with the Kenan Fellows Program at NC State University by acting as a Kenan Fellowship project mentor for Bruce Boller, a high school teacher from Bertie County, NC and Kenan Fellow awardee.

<http://www.ncsu.edu/kenanfellow>

X NESCENT EXTERNAL FUNDING

A. Funded

A Digital Repository for Preservation and Sharing of Data Underlying Published Works in Evolutionary Biology

National Science Foundation, BD&I (PI: Kathleen Smith)

NESCent Total Direct: \$1,907,531

NESCent Total Amount: \$2,180,169

09/01/2008 – 08/31/2012

Show Me the Evolution! Assessing Effectiveness of a New Teaching Resource

National Science Foundation, CCLI (PI: Kathleen Smith)

Total Direct Costs: \$117,976

Total Amount: \$150,000

01/01/2009 – 12/31/2010

INTEROP: International Virtual Data Center for the Biodiversity, Ecological and Environmental Sciences

Subaward through University of New Mexico (PI: William Michener)

National Science Foundation (PIs: Kathleen Smith and Hilmar Lapp)

NESCent Total Direct: \$39,535

NESCent Total Amount: \$50,803

07/15/2008 – 06/30/2011

Helping Interdisciplinary Vocabulary Engineering (HIVE)

Subagreement through UNC – Chapel Hill ((PI: J. Greenberg)

Institute for Museum and Library Sciences (PI: Kathleen Smith)

NESCent Total Amount: cost share only to Duke University

1/1/2009 – 6/30/2011

Linking Evolution to Genomics Using Phenotype Ontologies

Subaward through University of South Dakota (PI: Paula Mabee)

National Science Foundation BDI-0641025 (PI: Todd Vision)

NESCent Total Direct: \$853,338

NESCent Total Amount: \$1,050,945

06/01/2007 - 5/31/2010

Enhancement of the GBrowse Genome Annotation Browser

Subaward through University of California at Berkeley (PI: I. Holmes)

National Institutes of Health (PI: Todd Vision)

NESCent Total Direct: \$242,565
NESCent Total Amount: \$310,482 (D&I to UNC),
4/1/2007 - 3/31/2010

Development of the www.EcoliCommunity.org Information Resource

Subaward through Texas A&M Research Foundation (PI: Jim Hu)
National Institute of General Medical Science (PI: Todd Vision)
NESCent Total Direct: \$30,550
NESCent Total Amount: \$39,104
06/01/2007 – 05/31/2009

B. In Review

DataNetONE: Observation Network for Earth

Subaward through University of New Mexico (PI: W. Michener)
National Science Foundation (PI: Kathleen Smith)
NESCent Total Direct: \$390,490
NESCent Total Amount: \$501,780
10/1/2008 – 9/30/2013